

Technologies for ocean sensing (TechOceanS project)

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Keywords

Autonomous observations, sensors, samplers, imaging processing workflow, EOVs

Abstract

To address oceanographic community requirements for autonomous observations, new types of technology must be developed. New *in situ* sensors and samplers will have to measure new parameters, reduce in size and power consumption, increase measurement traceability, improve stability, reduce mechanical engineering requirements and improve communication and automatic data transfer to data centres. TechOceanS project will fill the existing gaps by delivering sensors, samplers and improved image processing workflows capable of remotely measuring essential ocean variables (EOVs) as well as regulatory targets such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive and OSPAR. To test the technology, a set of experiments and integration on a suit of platforms have been organised. The final tests will be carried out in Gran Canaria in spring 2024 where at least 7 new technologies developed in this project will be combined and integrated in 4 different autonomous vehicles. This unique opportunity will be used to provide a multidisciplinary practical training with students directly involved in the preparation (i.e. calibration/validation of sensors, preparation of the platforms) and management of deployments and will include at least 4 students and technicians from ODA recipient states.

In alignment with the objective of the UN Ocean Decade to secure “a transparent and accessible ocean”, TechOceanS has joined a growing partnership of initiatives and has a repository of methodological documents and candidate best practices in both the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS) and Better Biomolecular Ocean Protocols (BeBOP). These protocols are followed during sensor tests and are available for a community review in these platforms alongside sensor development templates developed in the project.

1. INTRODUCTION

The oceans cover over 70% of our planet (Attachment 2 to Tsukuba Communiqué, G7, 2016), directly contribute \$2.5trillion/yr in economic benefit, equivalent to the world's 7th largest economy and provide \$25 trillion in ecosystem services (Hoegh-Guldberg *et al.*, 2015). Whilst 90% of their value depends on healthy ecosystems, 30-35% of critical marine habitats are overused or have been destroyed, ocean acidity is up 26%, and oxygen is depleting in key areas (Brunson *et al.*, 2018). The international community is coordinating its response to these urgent challenges through the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, the Tsukuba Communiqué and the recommendations of the G7 expert workshop on future of the oceans and seas. Noting that 1) satellite observations provide unparalleled broad scale views of the ocean, but only see the surface, and 2) that research vessels are essential for process studies and benchmarking, but survey too infrequently and sparsely to address observation needs, the G7 expert workshop recommended sensor innovation particularly for biogeochemical and biological processes "from the range of available observing platforms and systems". Both scientists and other stakeholders (offshore engineering, fisheries and aquaculture industries) currently rely on carbon and cost intensive methods (e.g. manual sampling of decommissioned energy and aquaculture installations), while key variables to monitor ocean health remain critically under-sampled. Remote, *in situ* measurement systems can reduce the need, or potentially obviate these traditional methods, vastly improving data spatial and temporal resolution and filling capability gaps.

TechOceanS addresses these challenges through a balance of innovation and operations. Having selected the most promising technologies and leading researchers and engineers in the field, we proposed an ambitious yet deliverable programme of development and demonstration of measurement systems that can be deployed without the need for extensive logistics including research ships. TechOceanS targets variables with the greatest impact as prioritised through the Framework for Ocean Observing (FOO) / GOOS Essential Ocean Variable (EOV), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and direct stakeholder feedback.

2. THE PROJECT

The project will deliver 5 new sensor classes for biogeochemistry, biology and ecosystems addressing 10 of 19 EOVs, 31 of 73 subvariables, 6 of 9 MSFD targets together with microplastics and a range of biotoxins and contaminants. It will also develop a new image processing workflow for extracting EOVs (9) and MSFD (6) and litter measurements from images.

Poster presentations

TechOceanS has 3 technology development themes and a cross-cutting theme:

- Theme 1 aims to introduce new processes and technologies which will allow eDNA to be collected and sequenced continuously and in highly challenging subaquatic environments;
- Theme 2 is dedicated to the development of a suite of novel optical and imaging technology, analytic software and communication methods that will directly support the ambitious goals of the project, namely low cost, continuous remote autonomous ocean monitoring and measurement;
- Theme 3 aims to provide the capability to measure macro-nutrients, pollutants, microplastics, toxins and to analyse phytoplankton by flow cytometry, by “shrinking” the laboratory processes currently used and making them capable of functioning aboard small, remote AUVs (autonomous underwater vehicles) and other platforms.

It is clear from the scope of Themes 1, 2 and 3 that TechOceanS has very ambitious targets to bring such a wide range of innovations together in a single platform. For this reason, the project’s Theme 4 has been striving to ensure:

- All systems developed in lab settings are able to integrate with one another in the final design of the platform, which itself will function in challenging environments;
- The rigorous testing of all individual systems prior to integration to ensure they are each capable of achieving their targets in real-world operating environments;
- The processes, protocols and practices being developed over the course of the project are in line with the IOC-UNESCO Ocean Best Practices System and that these practices are assimilated into any designs or future revisions of TechOceanS technologies and methods.

Our future plans for testing and validation activities includes demonstration missions that will focus on aquaculture, built infrastructure (with relevance to offshore industries) and global ocean observing. Deployments are scheduled to take place between May and June 2024 in Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (Naples, Italy) and in March 2024 in the Canary Region and PLOCAN’s facilities and test site (Spain).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

TechOceanS project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme of the European Union under Grant Agreement N° 101000858 (TechOceanS). This output reflects only the authors' view and the Research Executive Agency (REA) cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

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